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Damage in hybrid jointed Glare structures under the quasi-static loading

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Research contents

Fiber metal laminates (FMLs), such as GLARE, i.e. glass-fiber reinforced aluminum, are nowadays used on the Airbus A380. The joint of GLARE is the weak position that should be considered clearly.

Research contents

Experimental researches

Axial tensile tests

DCB & ENF tests

- MTS testing machine
- VIC-3D DIC system
- Non-destructive technique(C-Scan)

DCB and ENF experimental facilities were prepared to study the adhesive properties of liquid shim mixed with microspheres. The two 2024-T3 aluminum alloy planes, which were prepared with the same surface treatment as that of the GLARE, were bonded by the liquid shim.

Research contents

Results and discussions

	Specimen 1	Specimen 1	Specimen 1	Average value
G_{IC} (N/mm)	0.4612	0.4626	0.4523	0.4587
G_{IIC} (N/mm)	0.9628	0.8337	0.8327	0.8697

- By investigating the load-displacement curves, load of DCB specimens dropped gradually, while load of ENF specimens dropped suddenly if crack started propagating forward.
- While crack growth reached a certain length, the fracture toughness of specimens maintained at a critical value that could be applied in simulation for delamination response

Research contents

Results and discussions

Simulation

- Plastic deformation of aluminum
- Ductile fracture
- Delamination between metal and p
- 3D Hashin criterion

Joint configuration	Sample number	Ultimate load (kN)	Ultimate failure displacement (mm)
Bolt jointed structures	1	10.259	0.736
	2	11.483	0.687
	3	10.687	0.765
	Simulation	9.257	0.701
Hybrid jointed structures	1	10.162	1.045
	2	10.322	1.124
	3	10.396	1.141
	Simulation	9.562	1.203

Research contents

Results and discussions

Secondary bending moment

Damage propagation

Bolt joint

Hybrid joint

Results and discussions

Delamination between metal and polymer

Research contents

Conclusions

The length of legend represents the destructiveness of each layer.

- Experiments and simulation were conducted to investigate the distortion of the aluminum alloy, bearing failure of the GFRP layers and inter-laminar delamination damage.
- The most obvious difference is an additional ultimate failure point 'C', which means that the liquid shim held up the tensile load prior to this point.
- Through non-destructive measurement and FE simulation, laminar delamination, aluminum alloy distortion and GFRP bearing damage were found around the bolt hole.
- The selection of a liquid shim should depend on the interlaminar properties of the GLARE laminate.

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Thanks

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